

The Impact of Greenwashing on Gen Z's Electronic Vehicle Purchase Intentions: the Mediating Role of Green Trust

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ABSTRACT: In the context of the growing trend toward sustainable consumption, electric vehicle (EV) manufacturers and marketers actively employ green communication strategies to attract young consumers, particularly Generation Z. However, the increasing prevalence of greenwashing - where firms exaggerate or misrepresent the environmental benefits of EVs while lithium-ion battery production processes contribute significantly to environmental pollution - raises questions regarding its impact on green trust and EV purchase intentions. This study adopts the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) framework to predict individual customers' beliefs and purchase intentions, particularly among Generation Z influenced by greenwashing. Data were collected from 416 survey respondents in Hanoi and analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS software. The results indicate that greenwashing exerts a significant negative effect on green trust and purchase intentions, while TPB constructs positively promote green purchase intentions. The findings highlight the need for firms to implement clear and transparent communication strategies to maintain trust and enhance consumer purchase intentions, avoid greenwashing activities, and encourage genuine green consumption.

KEYWORDS: Generation Z, greenwashing, green trust, electric vehicle purchase intention, Theory of Planned Behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

The transportation sector is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for 15.9% (Leichter, 2025), which has accelerated the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) as a cleaner alternative (Shui et al., 2024). The global EV market has grown rapidly, with over 14 million units sold in 2023 and projections exceeding 20 million by 2025 (IEA, 2025), reflecting a shift toward sustainable consumption. However, the rise of greenwashing has increased consumer skepticism toward environmental claims, potentially undermining trust and purchase intentions (Daou et al., 2025; Borah et al., 2024). In the EV sector, discrepancies between "green" marketing and actual environmental impacts—particularly in battery production—raise concerns about the credibility of sustainability commitments (Daou et al., 2025). Generation Z, known for strong environmental awareness and preference for responsible brands, significantly influences green consumption, especially in emerging markets like Vietnam (Prayag et al., 2022; Ko & Jeon, 2024). Despite prior research on greenwashing, its effects in the EV context and the mediating role of green trust remain underexplored (Liao & Wu, 2024).

Accordingly, this study addresses the following research questions:

- 1) How does the perception of greenwashing influence Generation Z consumers' green trust in electric vehicles?
- 2) What factors affect electric vehicle purchase intention in the context of greenwashing?
- 3) Does green trust play a mediating role in the relationship between greenwashing and electric vehicle purchase intention?

2. THEORY AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Theory framework

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) posits that behavioral intention is formed by an individual's attitude and subjective norms, reflecting personal evaluation and perceived social pressure regarding the performance of a behavior (Sciglimpaglia et al., 2020). Building upon this foundation, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) extends the model by incorporating perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991).

Within the TPB framework, attitude toward the behavior (ATT) reflects the degree to which an individual evaluates a behavior as favorable or unfavorable. Subjective norms (SN) represent the perceived social pressure from important reference groups, such as family, friends, or colleagues (Ajzen, 1991; Bamberg & Möser, 2007). Perceived behavioral control (PBC) refers to an individual's perception of their ability and available resources to perform the behavior, including factors such as financial capacity, opportunities,

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and external conditions (Ajzen, 1991). These three components interact to shape behavioral intention, which in turn predicts actual behavior (Ajzen, 1991).

2.2 Research Hypotheses

The Relationship Between Greenwashing and Green Trust

Greenwashing refers to making unsubstantiated or misleading claims about the environmental benefits of a product, service, technology, or company (Watson, 2017). Green trust reflects the extent to which consumers believe that electric vehicles truly deliver the environmental benefits as promised (Choe et al., 2021).

Previous studies consistently demonstrate that greenwashing negatively affects green trust. When environmental claims lack transparency or are misleading, consumers face difficulties in assessing their credibility, leading to diminished trust (Ha et al., 2022). Furthermore, greenwashing increases perceived risk and skepticism regarding corporate authenticity, potentially undermining trust in green marketing practices more broadly (Wang et al., 2020).

In the context of electric vehicles, although these products are associated with environmental benefits, concerns related to their lifecycle—particularly battery disposal—intensify doubts about their true sustainability. This makes consumers, especially Generation Z, more cautious in forming trust. Accordingly, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H1: Perceived greenwashing has a negative effect on green trust.

The Relationship Between Green Trust and TPB Components in Electric Vehicle Purchase Behavior

Prior studies in marketing and consumer behavior consistently indicate that trust—particularly green trust—positively influences the components of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), including attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Paul et al., 2023). In the context of transportation and services, TPB has been demonstrated as an effective framework for explaining mode choice behavior, with trust reinforcing TPB constructs and indirectly influencing behavioral intention (Borhan et al., 2017; Ibrahim et al., 2020).

However, in the context of electric vehicles—products characterized by high perceived risk and closely associated with environmental commitments—the relationship between green trust and TPB components remains insufficiently explored. Accordingly, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H2: Green trust positively influences attitude toward the behavior.

H3: Green trust positively influences subjective norms.

H4: Green trust positively influences perceived behavioral control.

The Relationship Between TPB Components and Electric Vehicle Purchase Intention

Electric vehicle purchase intention reflects the extent to which consumers are willing and committed to choosing environmentally friendly transportation over traditional fossil fuel-powered vehicles (Panda et al., 2020). Previous research suggests that a positive attitude is a fundamental determinant of consumers' purchase intention, particularly for environmentally friendly and high-involvement products (Erni et al., 2021; Kaur et al., 2022). Positive attitudes are shaped by beliefs and perceptions regarding environmental benefits, operating costs, performance, and sustainability value, which in turn enhance purchase intention and reduce practical barriers such as cost and infrastructure limitations.

Subjective norms are identified as a key determinant influencing green consumption and electric vehicle purchase intention through the impact of family, friends, and social reference groups (Sandman et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2022). Generation Z has a higher level of environmental awareness and is more sensitive to social issues than previous generations (Garai-Fodor et al., 2021). Particularly for Generation Z, strong engagement with social media amplifies the influence of social norms, as sustainable consumption behaviors are increasingly portrayed as socially desirable and trendy practices (Singh et al., 2022).

Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC) is a critical antecedent of behavioral intention, especially in the context of green consumption (Wang et al., 2020). When consumers perceive that they possess sufficient ability, resources, and opportunities to overcome barriers, PBC increases and strengthens their purchase intention.

Accordingly, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H5: Attitude toward the behavior positively influences electric vehicle purchase intention.

H6: Subjective norms positively influence electric vehicle purchase intention.

H7: Perceived behavioral control positively influences electric vehicle purchase intention.

Based on the theoretical foundations of greenwashing, green trust, and the Theory of Planned Behavior, this study proposes a research model:

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Figure 1: Model concept

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

This study employed a non-probability convenience sampling method. Data were collected using questionnaires distributed both directly and through social media platforms such as Zalo and Facebook to Generation Z individuals living, studying, and working in Hanoi over a three-month period from November 5, 2025 to January 22, 2026. Following Hair et al. (2019), the minimum sample size for multivariate analysis should be at least five to ten times the number of observed variables; with 28 observed variables, the required minimum sample size was 280. After data collection and screening, a total of 416 valid responses were retained for analysis. The data were analyzed using the PLS-SEM approach with SmartPLS 4 and SPSS 27, which is appropriate for examining complex structural models with small to medium sample sizes (Hair et al., 2017).

3.2 Survey Structure

The questionnaire consisted of two main parts. The first part collected demographic information (e.g., gender, age, education level, and income). The second part included items measuring greenwashing, green trust, attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, all designed using a five-point Likert scale to assess respondents' level of agreement, where (1) indicates "strongly disagree" and (5) indicates "strongly agree."

Specifically, greenwashing was adapted from Braga Junior et al. (2019) with five observed variables; green trust was adapted from Chen (2010) with four observed variables; attitude was adapted from (Erni et al, 2021) with five observed variables; subjective norms were with five observed variables; perceived behavioral control included four observed variables adapted from Paul et al. (2016); and electric vehicle purchase intention was measured using five observed variables adapted from (Liao & Wu, 2024).

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1. Research sample

After the data screening process, a total of 416 valid questionnaires were retained for analysis. Demographic data were processed using SPSS 27 and are summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

Variable Description		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	195	46,9
	Female	221	53,1
Age	Under 18 years old	28	6,7
	18 - 22 years old	268	64,4
	23 - 25 years old	87	20,9
	26 - 30 years old	33	7,9
Income	Under 5 million VND/month	251	60,3

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	5 - 15 million VND/month	105	25,2
	Over 15 million VND/month	60	14,4
Main source of income	Family support	185	44,5
	Employment	229	55,0
	Social assistance / government support	2	0,5
	Other	0	0

In terms of gender, the sample is relatively balanced, with 46.9% male and 53.1% female respondents. Regarding age, the majority of participants fall within the 18–22 age group (64.4%), followed by those aged 23–25 (20.9%), 26–30 (7.9%), and under 18 (6.7%), indicating a diverse distribution within Generation Z.

With respect to income, most respondents reported a monthly income of below VND 5 million (60.3%), followed by those earning between VND 5–15 million (25.2%) and above VND 15 million (14.4%). The primary sources of income are employment (55%) and family support (44.5%). Overall, the sample structure reflects typical characteristics of Generation Z, ensuring its representativeness for analyzing behaviors and perceptions related to green consumption.

4.2. Evaluation of the measurement Model

Reliability: The study evaluates the measurement model to confirm the reliability and validity of the constructs (Kante & Michel, 2023). Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR); convergent validity was evaluated through average variance extracted (AVE) and outer loadings; while discriminant validity was examined using the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT). These criteria represent standard benchmarks for assessing reflective measurement models in PLS-SEM. The analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4, and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Measurement model testing

Construct	Item	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Perceived Greenwashing (GW)	GW1	0,844	0,923	0,942	0,766
	GW2	0,890			
	GW3	0,878			
	GW4	0,873			
	GW5	0,888			
Green Trust (GT)	GT1	0,896	0,919	0,942	0,804
	GT2	0,899			
	GT3	0,901			
	GT4	0,889			
Attitude toward Behavior (ATT)	ATT1	0,798	0,860	0,899	0,640
	ATT2	0,767			
	ATT3	0,785			

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	ATT4	0,795			
	ATT5	0,851			
Subjective Norms (SN)	SN1	0,874	0,900	0,926	0,714
	SN2	0,835			
	SN3	0,833			
	SN4	0,870			
	SN5	0,812			
Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)	PBC1	0,817	0,823	0,882	0,652
	PBC2	0,813			
	PBC3	0,824			
	PBC4	0,774			
Electric Vehicle Purchase Intention (EVPI)	EVPI1	0,835	0,911	0,933	0,737
	EVPI2	0,868			
	EVPI3	0,860			
	EVPI4	0,850			
	EVPI5	0,879			

First, scale reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The results indicate that all constructs have values ranging from 0.823 to 0.923, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021), thereby demonstrating high internal consistency. At the same time, none of the values exceed 0.95, suggesting the absence of item redundancy and supporting discriminant validity (Silva-Quiroz & Rioseco-Pais, 2025; Moirón Vallar et al., 2024). Therefore, the measurement scales are considered reliable and suitable for subsequent analyses.

Next, composite reliability (CR) was employed to further confirm these results, with values ranging from 0.882 to 0.942, all above the 0.7 threshold (Hair et al., 2022), indicating strong stability and consistency of the constructs. Regarding convergent validity, all outer loadings meet the required criteria, ranging from 0.767 to 0.901 and exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.7 (Götz et al., 2009; Hair et al., 2019; Hair Jr et al., 2022). This indicates that the observed variables adequately represent their respective latent constructs and achieve convergent validity; therefore, they were retained for further analysis.

Convergent validity: Convergent validity was further assessed using the average variance extracted (AVE). According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), an AVE value greater than 0.5 indicates that the majority of the variance in the observed variables is explained by the latent construct. This criterion is also supported by Hair et al. (2021), who suggest that $AVE \geq 0.5$ is required to establish convergent validity. The results show that AVE values range from 0.640 to 0.804, all exceeding the recommended threshold. This confirms that all constructs in the model achieve satisfactory convergent validity.

Discriminant validity: After establishing reliability and convergent validity, the study proceeded to assess discriminant validity to ensure clear distinctions among the latent constructs. Discriminant validity was evaluated using the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT), following the recommendations of Hair et al. (2019), with threshold values of < 0.85 (strict criterion) or < 0.90 (acceptable criterion) (Hair et al., 2019; Henseler et al., 2015). The results indicate that the constructs generally meet the discriminant validity requirements, confirming that they are distinct and adequately capture different latent concepts.

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Table 3: Differential Testing (HTMT)

	ATT	EVPI	GT	GW	PBC	SN
ATT						
EVPI	0,690					
GT	0,593	0,711				
GW	0,419	0,412	0,596			
PBC	0,742	0,898	0,714	0,485		
SN	0,778	0,812	0,760	0,411	0,897	

4.3 Structural model evaluation

Check the collinearity of independent variables

Before testing the structural model, the study assessed multicollinearity among predictor variables using the variance inflation factor (VIF), while also examining common method bias (Zafar et al., 2019). The results indicate that VIF values range from 1.000 to 3.053, all below the threshold of 5, which is acceptable in behavioral research (Hair et al., 2019). Some constructs, such as green trust (GT) and the relationship between greenwashing (GW) and GT, exhibit VIF values of 1.000, indicating a high level of independence. Overall, no significant multicollinearity issues were detected in the model.

Table 4: Multicollinearity of the Measurement Scales

	ATT	EVPI	GT	GW	PBC	SN
ATT		2,031				
EVPI						
GT	1,000				1,000	1,000
GW			1,000			
PBC		2,672				
SN		3,053				

Table 5: Index results of the structure model

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient (β)	Standard Deviation (stdev)	T statistics	P value	f square	Validity
H1	GW -> GT	-0,552	0,039	14,173	0,000	0,439	Accepted
H2	GT -> ATT	0,540	0,040	13,339	0,000	0,411	Accepted
H3	GT -> SN	0,695	0,031	22,587	0,000	0,934	Accepted
H4	GT -> PBC	0,630	0,034	18,332	0,000	0,659	Accepted
H5	ATT -> EVPI	0,114	0,044	2,605	0,009	0,019	Accepted
H6	SN -> EVPI	0,253	0,065	3,920	0,000	0,063	Accepted
H7	PBC -> EVPI	0,520	0,060	8,667	0,000	0,305	Accepted

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Hypothesis	Path Coefficient (β)	Standard Deviation (stdev)	T statistics	P value	Validity
GW -> GT -> ATT	-0,298	0,028	10,755	0,000	Accepted
GW -> GT -> SN	-0,384	0,029	13,030	0,000	Accepted
GW -> GT -> PBC	-0,348	0,032	10,830	0,000	Accepted
GT -> ATT -> EVPI	0,062	0,025	2,487	0,013	Accepted
GT -> SN -> EVPI	0,176	0,046	3,801	0,000	Accepted
GT -> PBC -> EVPI	0,328	0,036	9,166	0,000	Accepted

The results further show that all hypothesized relationships are statistically significant at the 5% level, with p-values below 0.05 (Hair et al., 2019). Notably, most relationships achieve a very high level of significance ($p < 0.001$), indicating strong robustness of the findings. In terms of standardized path coefficients (β) and t-values, the results demonstrate strong and stable effects. Specifically, the relationship between GT and subjective norms (SN) shows a coefficient of $\beta = 0.695$ ($t = 22.587$), while perceived behavioral control (PBC) significantly influences electric vehicle purchase intention (EVPI) ($\beta = 0.520$; $t = 8.667$). In addition, the negative effect of GW on GT ($\beta = -0.552$; $t = 14.173$) is substantial. All t-values exceed the critical threshold of 1.96, confirming the reliability of the estimates, and the signs of the coefficients are consistent with theoretical expectations.

The results also indicate that all indirect effects are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), with most reaching a high level of significance ($p < 0.001$) (Hair et al., 2019). This confirms the mediating role of green trust (GT). Specifically, the indirect paths $GW \rightarrow GT \rightarrow SN$ ($\beta = -0.384$; $t = 13.030$) and $GW \rightarrow GT \rightarrow PBC$ ($\beta = -0.348$; $t = 10.830$) demonstrate strong effects, while $GW \rightarrow GT \rightarrow ATT$ ($\beta = -0.298$; $t = 10.755$) also shows a significant impact. All t-values exceed 1.96, reinforcing the robustness of the estimates and highlighting the pivotal mediating role of GT.

The study employed f^2 to assess effect sizes, which range from 0.019 to 0.935. Greenwashing has a large effect on green trust ($f^2 = 0.439$), while green trust strongly influences attitude ($f^2 = 0.411$), perceived behavioral control ($f^2 = 0.659$), and especially subjective norms ($f^2 = 0.934$). For EV purchase intention, attitude has a small effect ($f^2 = 0.019$), whereas perceived behavioral control ($f^2 = 0.143$) and subjective norms ($f^2 = 0.140$) show moderate effects, indicating that Gen Z's intention is driven more by behavioral control and social influence.

The PLS-SEM results indicate that all endogenous constructs achieve R^2 values above the 0.25 threshold, ranging from 0.291 to 0.669, reflecting moderate explanatory power. EV purchase intention (EVPI) shows strong predictive capability with $R^2 = 0.669$, while green trust ($R^2 = 0.305$), subjective norms ($R^2 = 0.483$), attitude ($R^2 = 0.291$), and perceived behavioral control ($R^2 = 0.397$) further confirm that greenwashing and related factors significantly shape trust, attitudes, and EV purchase intention among Generation Z.

Figure 2: PLS-SEM analysis results of the research model

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CONCLUSION ON THE HYPOTHESES

The results support H1, indicating that perceived greenwashing negatively affects green trust. When consumers doubt environmental claims, their trust declines, consistent with prior studies (Wang et al., 2025), particularly in the context of Generation Z, who have access to diverse information sources.

For H2, H3, and H4, green trust positively influences the components of the Theory of Planned Behavior, including attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, consistent with Shah et al. (2023).

Regarding H5, H6, and H7, all TPB components positively affect EV purchase intention, with subjective norms emerging as the strongest predictor. These findings align with previous studies (Shah et al., 2023; Fleseriu et al., 2020; Skallerud & Armbrecht, 2025), highlighting the importance of social influence and the reduction of barriers in promoting green consumption behavior.

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

The study identifies green trust as a key mediating factor in the relationship between perceived greenwashing and EV purchase intention among Generation Z. Unlike prior studies (Wang et al., 2025; Jokinen et al., 2012), which primarily focused on direct effects, these findings clarify the underlying psychological mechanism: perceived greenwashing increases skepticism, which in turn reduces green trust and indirectly lowers purchase intention. This highlights the critical importance of transparency in an era of increasing green marketing and widespread access to information.

Furthermore, within the Theory of Planned Behavior framework, perceived behavioral control is identified as the strongest determinant of EV purchase intention, contrasting with many previous studies that emphasized the role of attitude (Shalender & Sharma, 2021; Hasan, 2021). The results suggest that for Generation Z, practical factors such as financial capability, charging infrastructure, and convenience play a more decisive role. This underscores the importance of feasibility and enabling conditions in promoting sustainable consumption behavior.

5. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTIONS

This study makes several theoretical contributions by extending the understanding of greenwashing in the context of electric vehicle consumption in emerging markets. First, it provides additional empirical evidence by examining greenwashing in the electric vehicle sector—an area that remains underexplored in prior research, which has largely focused on green consumer products in general. Moreover, by focusing on Generation Z, the study sheds light on the sustainable consumption behavior of a young cohort that is highly sensitive to environmental issues but has not been sufficiently addressed in previous studies.

Second, the study clarifies the underlying mechanism of greenwashing effects by identifying the mediating role of green trust in the relationship between perceived greenwashing and purchase intention. In doing so, it contributes to the existing literature, which has predominantly examined direct effects. Furthermore, integrating greenwashing into the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) framework extends the applicability of this theory in contexts characterized by misleading environmental information.

Third, the findings provide new evidence by demonstrating that perceived behavioral control is the strongest predictor of electric vehicle purchase intention. This enriches TPB-related research and highlights the critical role of feasibility-related factors in shaping green consumption behavior.

The study also offers important practical implications. The findings emphasize that electric vehicle companies should prioritize transparency in environmental information to mitigate the negative impact of greenwashing on consumer trust, particularly among Generation Z. Shifting from symbolic communication toward a data-driven and evidence-based approach—through the disclosure of emissions metrics, energy efficiency indicators, and recyclability—can help strengthen green trust.

In addition, firms should build trust through environmental certifications and long-term sustainability commitments. Independent certification mechanisms and transparent emission reduction strategies not only enhance the credibility of environmental claims but also reinforce consumers' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control regarding electric vehicle purchases.

Moreover, improving the electric vehicle ecosystem plays a crucial role in enhancing perceived behavioral control—the most influential factor affecting purchase intention. Firms should collaborate with relevant stakeholders to expand charging infrastructure, provide flexible financial solutions, and ensure transparency in operating costs, thereby increasing accessibility and the practical feasibility of electric vehicle adoption.

Finally, companies should leverage social norms in their communication strategies, particularly through digital platforms and online communities, to foster purchase intentions among Generation Z. Developing community-based messages and promoting sustainable lifestyles can positively shape consumer behavior and enhance the attractiveness of electric vehicles in the market.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The findings indicate that perceived greenwashing has a significant negative effect on green trust among Generation Z, which in turn indirectly reduces their intention to purchase electric vehicles. Green trust emerges as a central construct in the model, as it is not only influenced by greenwashing but also positively affects all three components of the TPB, namely attitude, subjective norms,

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and perceived behavioral control. Notably, green trust plays a crucial mediating role, clarifying the mechanism through which perceived greenwashing influences purchase intention.

Additionally, all three components of the TPB have positive effects on electric vehicle purchase intention, with perceived behavioral control being the strongest predictor, followed by subjective norms and attitude. These results suggest that, for Generation Z, feasibility-related factors and practical conditions play a more important role than attitudes alone in driving sustainable consumption behavior.

This study has several limitations. First, the sample is limited to Generation Z consumers in Hanoi, which restricts the generalizability of the findings to other generational cohorts and regions in Vietnam. Second, the data were collected through self-reported questionnaires, which may be subject to response biases such as social desirability bias. Third, the cross-sectional research design captures relationships among variables at a single point in time and does not allow for the examination of changes in consumer perceptions and behaviors over time. Additionally, the research model includes only a limited number of variables and therefore may not fully capture other factors influencing electric vehicle purchase intention. Future research could expand the sample to include different generational groups and geographic regions, adopt mixed-method approaches combining qualitative and quantitative techniques, and employ longitudinal research designs. Furthermore, additional variables such as environmental awareness, perceived risk, technological readiness, social influence, and infrastructure conditions could be incorporated to enhance the explanatory power of the model.

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